

CoMSES Digest: Spring 2026

Volume 14, No. 1 Dec 16th 2025 - March 15th, 2026

Editor's Note

Greetings from the CoMSES Net team! My name is Isaac Ullah, and it is my pleasure to introduce myself as a newly elected member of the CoMSES Executive Board for the 2026-2028 term. Although I am new to the board, my connection to CoMSES is longstanding. I am a Professor of Anthropology/ Archaeology at San Diego State University, where I work on computational approaches to human and environmental systems, especially through agent-based modeling, spatial analysis, and interdisciplinary research on complex socioecological dynamics. I have long valued CoMSES as a rare and important space where models are not treated simply as end products, but as scholarly objects that can be shared, examined, reused, and improved through community practice.

As I begin my term on the board, I am especially interested in the role CoMSES continues to play in the broader world of computational modeling, both as infrastructure and as a hub for communication and community development. Good modeling practice depends on more than well-crafted code alone; it depends on clear documentation, communication, transparency, reproducibility, discoverability, and the willingness of researchers to open their code to peer review and reuse. CoMSES has upheld these values since its inception in 2007. As the organization has evolved and its membership has expanded, CoMSES has also provided forums, educational materials, and shared standards that raise the quality and accessibility of computational research. These are not secondary concerns; they are integral to what makes open modeling science possible.

My connection to CoMSES goes back to its formative years at Arizona State University. I began my PhD there in 2005 as Michael Barton's student, at a time when CoMSES was still taking shape. My own work focused primarily on archaeological modeling as part of the Mediterranean Landscape Dynamics (MedLanD) project. Although I was aware of the early CoMSES effort and the community around it, my direct involvement was at first fairly limited. That began to change toward the end of my graduate training and early career as CoMSES became more firmly established. After a couple of external post-graduate positions, I returned to ASU as a post-doc on the second round of MedLanD from 2014-2016, which is when we archived the MedLanD model in the CoMSES

library. That experience stuck with me.

My deeper engagement with CoMSES developed once I began my position at San Diego State University in 2016 and started to build a research and teaching program of my own. As I began creating models independently, CoMSES was the natural place to archive them, and the opportunity for code peer review quickly became one of the platform's most valuable contributions to my career profile. Over the years, I have archived five models through CoMSES, with four of them going through the peer review process. As I integrated modeling more fully into the archaeology curriculum at SDSU, I also came to rely increasingly on the model library as a teaching resource. Over time, I saw even more clearly how important CoMSES had become, not only as a repository, but as infrastructure for scholarly recognition. My peer-reviewed models were included in my tenure and promotion files, and in my recent promotion to full professor the value of peer-reviewed software was explicitly recognized by reviewers. That kind of recognition would have been far more difficult to imagine a decade ago; CoMSES helped make it possible.

As I have become more involved in the broader modeling community, including through the Open Modeling Foundation, I have come to appreciate even more fully the foundational role CoMSES plays in education, outreach, community building, and scientific capacity. Serving as a [peer reviewer](#) has been one way to give back to an organization that has mattered a great deal in my own work, and I would encourage others to consider doing the same. I have also enjoyed being interviewed twice for the "[Ten Minute Dialogs](#)" series on the [CoMSES YouTube Channel](#). I am glad now to have the opportunity to contribute further as a member of the board.

This issue of the Digest reflects many of these same themes. Across updates on AI-assisted workflows, documentation, education, outreach, events, and peer review, it highlights the many ways CoMSES continues to support not only the production of computational models, but also the broader ecosystem of practices that make those models useful, interpretable, and reusable. At a moment when AI-assisted tools are beginning to [reshape how many researchers approach coding, documentation, and analysis](#), communities like CoMSES become even more important as centers of institutional knowledge about models and modeling. New tools may accelerate parts of the modeling process, but they do not lessen the need for rigorous assumptions, transparent methods, reproducible workflows, and meaningful peer engagement. If anything, they make those commitments more important.

I am grateful for the opportunity to serve this community, and I look forward to learning from the many researchers, educators, developers, and reviewers who make CoMSES what it is. The strength of this organization has always rested not only in the technical systems it maintains, but also in the people who contribute their time, expertise, and imagination to a shared enterprise. I am pleased to be joining that effort in this new role.

[Isaac Ullah](#)

Professor of Anthropology;

Director of the Computational Archaeology Laboratory;

CoMSES News

AI Agents as Modeling Assistants

Over the past year, we've seen LLM-powered agents become remarkably capable. An agent, in this context, is an LLM running in a loop with access to tools: it can read and write files, execute commands, observe outputs, and iterate on its own. Coding agents (like [Claude Code](#), [OpenCode](#), etc.) built on this pattern have been rapidly adopted in software engineering, with many developers now writing very little code by hand. Adoption in many computational research settings has been slower. And not for no good reason, research software like simulation models, are often precise, carefully constructed artefacts rather than code that solves a practical problem as well as it needs to. For-profit businesses are much more willing to bet on AI-generated code and fork over the money for subscription plans that promise to multiply developer productivity. Researcher attitudes tend to be much more hesitant, and the lag in institutional pressure means that no one is forcing us to use such tools, but also that often no one is paying for us to experiment with them either.

But crafting the model itself is only a fraction of the work. Much of it is drudgery: wrangling data, piecing together visualizations, painstakingly creating documentation, interacting with HPC systems, and running analyses. Or ideals that we may fall short of due to finite time such as perfectly understandable, reproducible, and reusable code. So as long as AI is constrained by limited combinatorial creativity, and we are doing the research ourselves, this is where we can make the most use of these tools— using them as virtual assistants to offload the tedious work, freeing up our time.

A central aim of the research infrastructure work at CoMSES Net is to provide researchers with tools to more easily produce and use high quality research software. It is clear to us that many of our once lofty ambitions can now be realistically approached and solved by making use of agents. Our initial experiments in things like generating structured documentation, visualizing data and simulations, as well as porting and refactoring model code, have shown a great deal of promise. The primary challenge in all of this is verification: making sure that generated outputs are correct, so this will remain a central focus as we move forward. In the near term, we plan on creating a community repository to demo [agent “skills”](#): sets of instructions, context, templates, and deterministic scripts that help agents carry out specialized tasks.

As always, we want researcher input to help guide these efforts. Are you using agentic AI in your work? What are the use-cases you'd like to see tackled? Skeptical? Or facing barriers in using these tools? We welcome general thoughts and discussion on these topics over at the [CoMSES Net forum](#), and if you are interested in collaborating or simply sharing your thoughts, we'd love to hear from you at editors@comses.net.

CoMSES Board Election Results: 2026-2028 Terms

As many of you may know, in the early weeks of 2026 we held our CoMSES Board Member Elections. Thank you so much to those of you who took the time to participate - and vote - in this critical aspect of CoMSES operations. With three incredible nominees for only two positions, this year's election proved to be very hotly contested - with all three nominees final results being very close.

It is with warmest congratulations that we officially announce the return of [Dale Rothman](#) for a second term, and welcome [Isaac Ullah](#) to the board for the first time. Both Dale and Isaac will serve as CoMSES Board members for the 2026-2028 term. You can read more about their work, and contributions to CoMSES from the provided links above - or from the <https://www.comses.net/about/people/> page.

On the Horizon for the CoMSES Education Arm

Recently, the efficacy of Large Language Models (LLMs) to program agent-based models has become a topic of considerable interest and debate. At present CoMSES has not come to any firm conclusions on the use of LLMs for coding, however, the CoMSES research team has been exploring the use of LLMs to generate an ODD from model code. The ODD protocol is a standardized way to describe agent-based models introduced by Volker Grimm and colleagues that model authors include with their code at CoMSES. In the upcoming months researchers at CoMSES plan to release an outline of recommended approaches to generating an ODD with an LLM on the [CoMSES site](#) and in a video on our [YouTube channel](#). This is an exciting opportunity - please 'watch this space' and we will have a more detailed update for you on these developments in a future Digest once these resources are complete and available.

Sean Bergin

Special Event Reminder: SIMBRA

Registration is now open for the [1st Brazilian Interdisciplinary Symposium on Agent Based Models](#). This conference aims to create a meeting space for researchers and students from different fields to discuss, experiment with, and disseminate the use of agent-based models as a tool for representing and investigating complex phenomena. The conference is co-sponsored by CoMSES.Net and the Open Modeling Foundation, two international organizations dedicated to promoting best practices in computational modeling. The program will include keynote lectures by leading experts in the field, roundtable discussions, and a NetLogo workshop led by national and international specialists.

The conference will take place from May 27 to 29 at the School of Public Health of the Universidade de São Paulo, in a hybrid format. For more

information, visit the conference web site: <https://simbra.com.br>. Additional details are available at: <https://presskit.simbra.com.br> (Brazilian Portuguese) Full event details can be reviewed at the end of 'Upcoming Deadlines' section below.

Keep Your CoMSES Profile Updated

Please consider keeping the CoMSES community informed by updating your user account on CoMSES Net! Let fellow researchers and modelers get to know you by including a biography, research interests, and/or institutional affiliation. [Click here](#) to edit your profile and while you are at it, why not link your account to GitHub and ORCID!

As always, feel free to join the conversation by visiting the [Forums tab](#), or by starting a discussion on a specific model, event, or job posting. If you register your affiliation on your profile page, it will help us fill out our new member profile map: <https://www.comses.net/about/metrics!>

Calendar of Events

Follow the links to the local event organizers for the latest information or go to <https://comses.net/events/> for a listing of all recent events. You can also subscribe to new events by following us on [Twitter/X](#) or subscribing to our [RSS feeds](#).

Upcoming Deadlines

Social Simulation Conference 2026 - Durham, UK

Dates: August 24-28, 2026;
Submission deadline: April 12, 2026

(Adapted from original event website)

The conference is one of the key activities of the European Social Simulation Association (ESSA), aimed at promoting social simulation in Europe and elsewhere. This year's special theme is "Embracing the social in computational social science." The Durham Research Methods Centre is delighted to host this conference as part of our commitment to promoting cutting edge methods in social science.

Workshops hosted include: Emerging Practices in Science Communication for Social Simulation, Models of Human Decision: Exchange Hub, Ethnographic Methods and Social Simulation, and more.

Paper submission information:

When submitting your paper, you will be asked to choose a submission type and relevant special track(s). The four types of submissions available are:

- Poster: 300-500 word abstract, to be presented as a poster at the dedicated poster session at the conference

- Extended abstract: 3-4 pages, can be work in progress
- Full paper for presentation only: 6-12 pages, should be complete papers with model design, results and conclusions (or other appropriate content), but can include work in progress elements
- Full paper intended for proceedings: 6-12 pages, should be complete papers with model design, results and conclusions (or other appropriate content). These papers may be subject to additional review.

The deadline for submission is 12 April 2026. We expect to notify authors of accepted submissions in May.

To submit a paper, please follow the link to the submission site. Note that you will need to register on the site before you are able to submit. LaTeX and Word templates for abstracts and papers are available from the Springer site.

When you submit your paper, you will be asked to select relevant special tracks. Please indicate the special tracks that you feel your paper is most likely to fit. Note, however, that your paper may be allocated to a different special track if there is a better fit once we can see all the accepted papers.

Multi-Platform International Summer School on Agent-Based Modelling and Simulation (MISSABMS) 2026

Dates: June 15-26, 2026;

Registration Deadline: April 15, 2026

MISSABMS 2026 - The Multi-Platform International Summer School on Agent-Based Modelling & Simulation for renewable resources management.

By taking part in this course, you will gain a modelling culture and learn the different skills required for building agent-based models (ABM) applied to sociological, ecological or socio-ecological systems. MISS-ABMS is multi-platform: You will eventually work with only 1 platform but you will be introduced to 3 of the most prominent agent-based modeling platforms in the field of socio-ecological science: NetLogo, GAMA, Cormas.

You will have many opportunities to collaborate with participants using the other platforms. Before making your choice, light is shed on the advantages and disadvantages of each one.

Further information can be found here: <https://www.agropolis.fr/ABOUT-MISS-ABMS>

1.º Simpósio Interdisciplinar Brasileiro de Modelos Baseados em Agentes (1st Brazilian Interdisciplinary Conference on Agent Based Modeling)

Dates: May 27-29, 2026

The 1st Brazilian Interdisciplinary Symposium on Agent-Based Models (SIMBRA) proposes to create a meeting space for researchers and students from

different fields to discuss, experiment with, and disseminate the use of Agent-Based Models (ABMs) as tools for modeling and investigating complex phenomena. The central objective of the Symposium is to form a national interdisciplinary community dedicated to this approach. Planned to take place from May 27 to 29, 2026, at the School of Public Health of the University of São Paulo, the event will be free of charge and hybrid, combining in-person and virtual activities.

The initiative is led by Aline Martins de Carvalho, a professor at the School of Public Health of the University of São Paulo (FSP/USP), and organized by the Agent-Based Modeling Study Group, part of the Sustentarea Research Group and University Extension Center (FSP/USP). It is supported by the Open Modeling Foundation (OMF) and CoMSES.net, two well-established international associations that coordinate initiatives to ensure best practices within the modeling community.

The program, structured around thematic axes, will include lectures, roundtables, tutorials, and workshops on platforms such as NetLogo, Gama, and Mesa, as well as other practice-oriented tools, conducted by national and international specialists, among them Michael Barton (Director of OMF and CoMSES.net, and professor at the School of Complex Adaptive Systems (SCAS), Arizona State University (ASU)), Bernardo Furtado (researcher at the Institute for Applied Economic Research (IPEA)), and Leandro Garcia (professor at the School of Medicine, Dentistry, and Biomedical Sciences, Queen's University Belfast (QUB)).

Guided by the principles of horizontality, collaboration, and accessibility, the symposium seeks to foster exchanges between beginners and experts, promoting an open and participatory scientific practice oriented toward understanding and solving contemporary challenges.

Model Library

Newly Reviewed

6 models passed CoMSES's [peer review process](#) this quarter!

CoMSES is always looking for new model reviewers! As such we welcome self-nomination. If you would like to join our reviewer network, we invite you to do so by either completing [this short Google Poll](#), or by creating a peer reviewer profile under “Edit Profile” on your [comses.net](#) account.

New Model Uploads

Sixteen new models were published in the [CoMSES Model Library](#) on a wide variety of topics that illustrate the depth and breadth of our community. These include:

- Exploring the [emergence of multi-zonal resource management systems across Andean ecological landscapes](#)
- Investigating the [evolution of online protests and repression in authoritarian](#)

[contexts](#)

- Simulating [forest degradation under different logging approaches](#)
- Evaluating [market equilibria as impacted by misvaluation in the bargaining process](#)
- Studying [market tipping point development resulting from green consumption choices at the household level](#)

These models and more can be discovered at the [CoMSES Model Library](#) - you can also keep up-to-date with newly published models on our [Twitter/X](#) and [RSS](#) feeds.

Most Downloaded Models

Published models were downloaded a total of 1503 times this quarter, across 472 unique codebases. Here are the top five:

1. [Dawkins Weasel](#) by Kristin Crouse (256 downloads)
2. [Evolution of Sex](#) by Kristin Crouse (244 downloads)
3. [Multilevel Group Selection I](#) by Garry Sotnik (23 downloads)
4. [Relative Agreement Model and Network Structure](#) by David Adelberg (16 downloads)
5. [BENCHv.2 Model](#) by Leila Niamir (12 downloads)

Here at CoMSES we love to know how and why you use the models available in our library - as this not only helps us address gaps, but also better understand our users. If you would like to briefly share your download experiences with us, you can either complete this [short google form](#), or contact us any time at editors@comses.net - we look forward to hearing from you as well as look forward to seeing which models will appear in next quarter's top 5!

Twitter

YouTube

[Visit CoMSES.Net](#)

CoMSES Net is headquartered in
The School of Complex Adaptive Systems
College of Global Futures

College of Global Futures

777 E. University Dr, Tempe AZ 85287-7904, USA